

Computation of the Riemann Zeta Function for deriving the Euler Product

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Abstract: The Euler product is an infinite product of many functions in the multiplicative number theory. A completely multiplicative function gives the Euler product which is equal to the Riemann zeta function. This paper presents the computation of the Riemann zeta function for equalizing the Euler product. The Riemann zeta function plays a vital role in the analytic number theory and has applications in applied statistics, physics, and probability theory.

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1. Introduction

Euler product [1, 2] is used to predict a series that generates the infinite functions of multiplicative number theory, which is a subfield of analytic number theory dealing with prime numbers. In the analytic number theory, the completely multiplicative function $f(x) = n^{-1}$ gives the Euler product representation for the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$.

2. Riemann Zeta Function

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ for all complex numbers such as $s = a + ib$ is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = 1^{-s} + 2^{-s} + 3^{-s} + 4^{-s} + 5^{-s} + \dots = \sum n^{-s}, \quad \forall \Re(s) > 1.$$

Where $\Re(s)$ is the real part of all complex numbers \mathbb{C} such as $s \in \mathbb{C}$.

Alternatively, the Riemann zeta function [1, 2] is represented by:

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2n-1)^s + (2n)^s}{[n(4n-2)]^s}, \quad \forall \Re(s) > 1.$$

Let us prove this equation.

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{8^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \frac{1}{10^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \left[\frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \dots \right] + \left[\frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \dots \right] = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(2n-1)^s} + \frac{1}{(2n)^s} \right].$$

$$\therefore \zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2n-1)^s + (2n)^s}{[n(4n-2)]^s}.$$

The Riemann zeta function is the most important special function in the significantly large family of zeta-functions.

3. Proving the Euler Product from Riemann Zeta Function

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{8^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \dots$

Let us prove the Euler product from the following computation of Riemann Zeta function.

$$\frac{1}{2^s} \zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{8^s} + \frac{1}{10^s} + \frac{1}{12^s} + \frac{1}{14^s} + \frac{1}{16^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) - \frac{1}{2^s} \zeta(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \frac{1}{11^s} + \frac{1}{13^s} + \frac{1}{15^s} + \frac{1}{17^s} + \dots$$

$$i. e., \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \frac{1}{11^s} + \frac{1}{13^s} + \frac{1}{15^s} + \dots$$

$$\frac{1}{3^s} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \frac{1}{15^s} + \frac{1}{21^s} + \frac{1}{27^s} + \frac{1}{33^s} + \frac{1}{39^s} + \frac{1}{45^s} + \dots$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) - \frac{1}{3^s} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{11^s} + \frac{1}{13^s} + \frac{1}{17^s} + \dots$$

$$i. e., \left(1 - \frac{1}{3^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{11^s} + \frac{1}{13^s} + \frac{1}{17^s} + \frac{1}{19^s} + \dots$$

If the above processes are continued, the multiples of prime factors such as 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, ..., are removed and, at the end, the multiplication of the Riemann zeta function and reciprocal of the Euler product becomes 1.

$$\dots \dots \dots \left(1 - \frac{1}{13^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{11^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{7^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{5^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{3^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1.$$

$$i. e., \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1, \text{ where } \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}\right) \text{ is the reciprocal of Euler product.}$$

Here, $p_1^s = 2^s$, $p_2^s = 3^s$, $p_3^s = 5^s$, $p_4^s = 7^s$, $p_5^s = 11^s$, $p_6^s = 13^s$, $p_7^s = 15^s$, $p_8^s = 17^s$, ...

By simplifying the equation $\prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1$, we obtain the Euler product as follows:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1 \Rightarrow \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{\prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}\right)}$$

$$\Rightarrow \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_1^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_2^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_3^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_4^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_5^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_6^s}\right) \dots}$$

$$\Rightarrow \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_1^s}\right)} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_2^s}\right)} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_3^s}\right)} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_4^s}\right)} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_5^s}\right)} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_6^s}\right)} \dots$$

Therefore, $\zeta(s) = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}\right)}$, where $\prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}\right)}$ denotes the Euler product.

4. Conclusion

In the article, the author has derived the Euler product from the Riemann zeta function. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

References

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